

Case Study

Comprehensive Strategic Analysis for Determining Strategic Policies at Pt. Lmc

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Abstract

This article aims to explain the processes carried out by management at PT. LMC is used to determine company strategy for partnership activities. Several analyses are carried out to determine the company's strategy, such as market analysis, industry analysis, company analysis, SWOT analysis, and risk analysis. After conducting various analyses, company management can formulate a strategic plan, determine a partnership strategy model, and implement the strategy that has been chosen while still paying attention to possible risks. This research uses a qualitative analysis approach with a case study method. By conducting a comprehensive analysis, the management of PT. LMC can determine strategic plans effectively and implement partnership programs consistently while minimizing possible risks. Apart from that, the partnership operational division can carry out the strategy in stages with clear goals and targets to be more efficient. Management can continue to carry out regular monitoring activities to see whether the partnership program is still running well and making a contribution to the company. This article discusses the process of determining company strategy based on comprehensive analysis, which combines several analyses so that management can evaluate policies and supervise them effectively.

Keywords: Company analysis, Company Strategy, industry analysis, Strategy analysis, SWOT analysis.

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Introduction

Every business activity requires a strategy to achieve the goals it wants to achieve because by determining this strategy, it is hoped that a company can carry out operational activities more effectively. Strategic decision-making is one of the most critical aspects of management today and plays a vital role in achieving company success and survival. This factor is caused by fast changes in the business world, making it difficult for management to make decisions (Papulova & Gazova, 2016). The company concept in determining strategy has become necessary in the contemporary era (Carter, 2013), replacing management activities, such as administrative activities, with planning activities. The term "strategy" originates from the military domain and derives from the Greek word "strategos," which means general (Mackay & Zundel, 2017; Tzu, 2002). Over time, the concept of strategy has expanded and found applications in various human endeavors, notably in business strategy. Understanding the competitive landscape and interpreting the ramifications of competition within the business realm poses a significant challenge for business strategists (Cattani et al., 2017). Consequently, there is a pressing need for research studies to reinvigorate the examination of categories and competition within strategic management.

Throughout history, numerous scholars have delved into the concept of strategy. Chandler (1969) posits that strategy entails defining a company's long-term goals and objectives, implementing actions, and allocating resources necessary to achieve these objectives. Andrews (1987) characterizes strategy as a framework encompassing goals, policies, objectives, and detailed plans to define the company's present or future business activities. Porter (1985), on the other hand, defines strategy as the selection of a specific set of activities wherein the company excels, aiming to establish sustainable differentiation within the market. These distinctions stem from the chosen activities and how they are executed.

Alternatively, Hutzschenreuter and Kleindienst (2006) argued that the mechanical perspective was overly restrictive and advocated a dynamic and organic viewpoint. Emerging insights from natural and social sciences indicate that strategic processes extend beyond rationalist paradigms of individual actors. Instead, they emphasize the significance of soft variables and acknowledge the intricate nature of reality. The authors contend that whereas the mechanical approach to strategy formulation is characterized by its discrete, directional, and differentiated nature, the organic perspective embodies dynamism, uncertainty, interactivity, and integration.

Concurrently, a fresh wave of scholarly inquiry emerged, delving into behavioral and organizational theory (Bowman & Hurry, 1993; Brahm, 1994; Brown & Eisenhardt, 1998; Itami, 1991; Mintzberg et al., 2005; Mintzberg & Waters, 1985). These researchers illuminated that strategy entails the adaptive coordination of circumstances and trajectories. As Chiavenato and Brito (2009) articulated, four fundamental components of strategy synergize with one another. The mission addresses inquiries regarding an organization's *raison d'être*. It delineates the business pursuits, the needs fulfilled by its offerings, the markets it serves, and its public perception. Vision elucidates the organizational aspirations for the near future, defining and depicting the desired future

state. Its purpose is to steer, regulate, and inspire the organization toward achieving its envisioned state. Values encapsulate principles, beliefs, and guidelines that govern an organization's management. Global objectives outline the desired outcomes within a specified timeframe. These elements mold the institutional ethos and underpin the organizational culture (Mao et al., 2017). The chief objective of defining company values is to furnish a sturdy reference framework.

Strategic management involves all team members, including managers, actively shaping and measuring the positive impact they can have on the success of the company's strategy (Jelonek et al., 2022). In its critical role, strategic management helps create a solid outlook and plan the core business mission. It also establishes strategic objectives by thoroughly analyzing the external and internal environment and selecting appropriate strategies (Habib & Hasan, 2017).

A detailed strategic vision and a designed business mission help managers answer the business's essence, leading to establishing strategic goals that provide answers about what the company wants to achieve (Thompson, 2004). Strategic management ensures that every step is based on thorough, in-depth analysis and systematic methods, ensuring consistency between strategic goals and the company's mission (C. Hill et al., 2015; Srivastava et al., 1998). Through a thorough analysis of the internal environment, such as human resources, finance, and management, as well as the external environment, which includes cultural, economic, social, industrial, and competitor aspects, strategic management ensures that the business strategy being proposed is a realistic choice (Fuertes et al., 2020a; Nag et al., 2007). As a travel guide, strategic management helps strategists build and choose the right and effective path to achieve company goals (Allen, 1977).

External and internal factors consistently impact the company's business endeavors. Thus, business strategy assists the company in guiding its future operations through analysis and anticipation of the business environment (Tran, 2022). A business running in a stable market may not require a particular strategy. Some people think that strategy is something complicated. After creating a strategy, sometimes the market changes, and we have to throw it away and start again. Some think running a daily business is already tiring enough, so they do not want to look far away, especially since it will be different tomorrow (Fuertes et al., 2020b). Business strategy helps companies capture opportunities and overcome threats to developing company resources. Business strategy helps companies optimize and use resources rationally, promoting business strengths (Becker & Schmid, 2020). The strategy establishes a path for business operations, facilitating the alignment of individuals with diverse interests toward a shared objective, thereby fostering collective growth within the company. Business strategy nurtures cohesive relationships among employees and between managers and employees, enhancing and fortifying the company's internal.

In the business world, various factors originating from the company's external and internal environment always influence business activities. Therefore, to achieve optimal sustainability and development, a company needs to have careful foresight, and this can be achieved through implementing business strategies. (Ricardianto et al., 2023). Sometimes, there is a view that businesses operating in stable markets do not need a

specific plan or that the plan itself is complicated and can be thrown away if the market changes (Galbreath, 2009). However, many successful companies are proud of the hard work, financial investment, and team collaboration they put into building a solid business strategy with a vision and mission emblazoned on their website (Eklund, 2020). In this context, PT. As an agribusiness company operating since 2012, LMC is also actively involved in development through strategy analysis and evaluation in their partnership division. This division focuses on establishing partnerships with farmers and, in 2023, will successfully expand its business in several regions. However, the company faced new challenges with the emergence of new competitors and the introduction of oil-producing crops.

To face increasingly fierce competition and as a step in expansion plans, the management of PT. LMC plans to expand the work area of its partnership division. Before going any further, they realize the importance of conducting a thorough analysis to ensure the best decision. Therefore, the company decides to perform a SWOT analysis, which includes an evaluation of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats that may affect the project or business. SWOT analysis is essential in understanding a company's internal and external environment. This analysis helps PT. LMC will design practical strategies for facing changes and challenges in the market. By combining a general view of business strategy and company development efforts, it is hoped that PT. LMC can identify growth opportunities, overcome weaknesses, and design appropriate strategies to expand their partnership division's work area. Thus, the research will significantly contribute to company management in implementing business strategies. This contribution is available because business strategy creates close relationships between employees and managers and becomes an effective tool in facing the complexity of competition in today's global market. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive analysis in determining company policies.

Theoretical basis

Corporate Strategy

Peppard and Ward (2016) state that each organizational strategy must delineate the company's desired destination and impartially assess its current stance to chart a course forward, considering options, alternatives, available resources, and necessary transformations. A company attains superior profitability within an industry by achieving higher prices or lower costs than its rivals; this attainment stems from operational efficiency or strategic positioning (Porter, 2008a). According to Rumelt (2012), a sound strategy encompasses a blend of analyses, concepts, policies, arguments, and actions tailored to address high-stakes challenges. Cost-based strategy represents a generic manifestation of strategic positioning (Machaczka & Stopa, 2022; Sutherland, 2007). The strategy formulation process transcends mere executive responsibility (Reitzig & Maciejovsky, 2015); instead, it involves all echelons of the organizational hierarchy in defining novel business approaches and initiating requisite actions (heads of business units, heads of products, heads of functional areas within a business or division, administrators, and supervisors). Scholars and practitioners increasingly favor sustainability (a holistic measure of economic, social, and environmental performance) (Searcy, 2012). Consequently, strategies must incorporate social sustainability,

generating value for shareholders and other stakeholders, including employees (Iazzolino & Laise, 2016). As posited (Radomska, 2015), sustainability considerations in strategy are evolving into an inherent aspect of business policy, pivotal for the company's operational and financial outcomes, such as cost minimization, cleaner production, and reduction of emissions (Henrique et al. et al. 2014). In supply chain management, sustainability emerges as a crucial concern, heralding a new paradigm of business thinking and a wellspring of competitive advantage (Detwal et al., 2023; Epstein & Roy, 2001).

Typically, creating a strategy begins with assessing the company's external environment, followed by formulating an action plan to enhance competitiveness (Král & Králová, 2016). A SWOT analysis is the predominant method for scrutinizing a company's situation, elucidating its strengths and opportunities alongside its weaknesses and the threats the market poses within its operational purview (Nikulin & Becker, 2015). To ensure the success of a strategy, one must implement appropriate measures. Ensuring the success of a strategy requires careful planning and execution; it must be imbued with several vital elements: clear, coherent, and enduring objectives, a comprehensive comprehension of the competitive landscape, an impartial evaluation of available resources, and pragmatic implementation strategies (C. et al. et al., 2014).

In crafting a strategy, other facets necessitate consideration without reliance on particular references. This fundamental concept involves organizational learning capacity, which is recognized as a critical factor in the performance of an entity. Application of this concept allows for in-depth analysis of the relationship between levels of organizational structure, overall organizational performance, and the organization's ability to learn (Hussein et al., 2016). Organizations that adopt an organizational learning culture are claimed to significantly increase their competitive advantage, enabling survival in a fiercely competitive environment (Kieser & Koch, 2008). This approach also results in improved company performance, supported by transactional organizational learning (Mallén et al., 2016; Norashikin et al., 2009). This process enables organizations to preserve knowledge and convey it to experts for establishing or restructuring new protocols. Numerous research endeavors, exemplified by the work of Power and Waddell (2004), underscore the correlation between self-employment and the capacity for organizational learning, serving as performance metrics that enhance a company's innovative potential. Enterprises evolve by reshaping and reconfiguring resources and capabilities (Garud & Nayyar, 1994). These transformations lie in pivotal choices concerning the optimal organizational framework conducive to attaining competitive advantage (Benavides et al., 2016).

Market analysis

Market analysis is a systematic process carried out to understand the market conditions of a product or service. The goal of market analysis is to gain a deep understanding of customer needs, competitors, industry trends, and other factors that may influence the performance of a product or service in the market (Danilova & Kuznetsova, 2020). General steps in market analysis include determining the objectives of the analysis, collecting primary and secondary data, analyzing competitors to understand their strengths and weaknesses, and the marketing strategies they use (Norsita & Hardiyanti,

2017). Customer analysis is also carried out to understand consumer profiles, behavior, and preferences. Market trend analysis is essential to identify significant changes in market needs or demands (Kongthanasuwan et al., 2023).

Industry analysis

Industrial analysis is a methodological approach utilized to scrutinize an industry or industrial sector, fostering the generation of novel insights (S. Aithal, 2017). A robust case study entails identifying problems, exploring potential solutions, and furnishing decision-makers with ample information and uncertainty to select the optimal course of action for the system (Power & Waddell, 2004). Within business case studies, industry and company analyses represent distinct methodologies employed to systematically examine an industry or company's business model or challenges, aiming to identify research-oriented problems and generate fresh insights or improved problem-solving approaches (Arize et al., 2012). Industry analysis, conducted through systematic methodologies and defined objectives, can be the foundation for research-oriented and instructional case studies. Developing case studies for research or teaching purposes often proves more feasible than empirical research. Therefore, students pursuing higher education can construct case studies grounded in industry analysis as part of their research endeavors, provided they systematically gather the requisite information (Paramadita & Hidayat, 2022).

Company Analysis

Company analysis represents a pivotal form of case study methodology within research methodology, widely embraced by novice and seasoned researchers in scientific inquiry. Advocates suggest integrating corporate analysis as a compulsory assignment across all business school curricula can engage students in research endeavors, fostering a profound understanding of business challenges and honing problem-solving skills crucial for effective organizational management and leadership (P. S. Aithal, 2017). By undertaking corporate analyses of national or international firms across different semesters within business management programs, both at undergraduate and graduate levels, and subsequently disseminating these analyses as case studies in academic journals, business schools can actively involve students in research and scholarly publication initiatives (P. S. Aithal, 2017; S. Aithal et al., 2016). Through company analysis, researchers delve into myriad facets of corporate management, navigating managers' daily scenarios, decisions, and problems.

Company analysis is a formidable instrument for crafting research-based and instructional case studies in business management domains. Beyond scrutinizing business models and strategies to attain organizational objectives, practical corporate analysis can investigate the roles of the board of directors, management, and shareholders in achieving investor value maximization, agency theory, addressing information asymmetry, and resolving conflicts of interest between management and shareholders (Porter, 1985, 2008b). It may also examine the board of directors' involvement in determining the optimal financing mix, investment, and dividend decisions. Moreover, company analysis encompasses the contributions of diverse stakeholders toward achieving organizational objectives. It can encompass various dimensions such as Product/Service analysis,

technology analysis, market demand analysis, competitor analysis, stock market investment analysis, current and future demand analysis, longitudinal company performance analysis, country-based geographic location analysis, leadership analysis, resource utilization analysis, industry sector analysis, business breakthrough analysis, growth analysis, financial performance analysis vis-à-vis competitors within the industry, as well as assessments of challenges, opportunities, investment attractiveness, environmental factors, and competitive strategy analysis for success (P. S. Aithal, 2017; Chan et al., 2015).

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis, which stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, is crucial in organizational strategic planning and management. The systems approach views the organization as a whole interacting with its environment, which consists of various sub-systems (GÜREL, 2017). SWOT analysis is essential in strategic management practice, enabling a comprehensive assessment of two organizational environments: internal and external. This process, known as a SWOT analysis, involves an in-depth examination of the organization and its environment. This examination comprises four primary elements: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. It aids in recognizing internal and external factors that impact organizational performance (Benzaghta et al., 2021). Strengths and opportunities benefit an organization, while weaknesses and threats can harm it. The effectiveness of an organization's strategy hinges on harmonizing internal strengths and weaknesses with opportunities and threats arising from the external environment.

Figure 1. SWOT Analysis
Source : Mumtaz, (2023)

SWOT analysis helps managers match an organization's resources and capabilities with the demands of its competitive environment. This approach recognizes that a successful strategy requires a deep understanding of the organization's internal advantages and constraints and the opportunities and challenges it faces externally

(Poniwatie et al., 2022; Ryana Devi et al., 2022). Using the SWOT matrix, managers can design effective action plans to optimize positive potential and overcome possible obstacles. Thus, SWOT Analysis is an evaluation tool and a robust strategic guide for organizations facing the complex dynamics of the business world (Benzaghta et al., 2021).

Risk Analysis

Risk analysis is a methodical procedure for identifying, evaluating, and managing potential risks that could impact the attainment of the objectives of a project, activity, or organization (Romanosky & Petrun Sayers, 2023). Risk can be defined as uncertainty relating to objectives, and risk analysis aims to identify and measure the extent to which these risks may affect the success of an initiative (Hock et al., 2019; Institute of Internal Auditor, 2022). The risk analysis procedure typically comprises several stages, including risk identification, evaluation, formulation of risk management strategies, and consistent monitoring and updating (Alazzabi et al., 2023; Verbano & Venturini, 2013).

Risk identification involves recognizing and documenting potential risks that may arise in a situation (Febrianti & Novita, 2021; Karanja, 2017). Risks can be financial, operational, technical, or environmentally related and originate from various sources, such as regulatory changes, market uncertainty, or software failure. Once risks are identified, the subsequent step is to evaluate the risk, which entails assessing the potential impact and likelihood of the risk occurring (Wicaksono, 2020). Risk identification helps identify the most significant risks and prioritize risk management.

Developing a risk management strategy involves planning actions to reduce the impact of a risk or the likelihood of a risk occurring. These strategies may include risk transfer through insurance, risk mitigation by implementing preventive measures, risk acceptance by understanding and accepting the consequences, or risk avoidance by changing plans or work methods. Risk monitoring and regular updates are essential to ensure that risk management strategies remain relevant as time passes and conditions change (Nurlaela & Suhendi, 2021; Wahyuni & Novita, 2021). Risk analysis is commonly applied in various contexts, including construction projects, finance, supply chain management, and business in general. The ultimate goal of risk analysis is to increase the likelihood of success of an initiative or activity by identifying, measuring, and managing possible uncertainties. It is an integral practice in proactive management, helping organizations to face uncertainty with informed and targeted strategies (Alazzabi et al., 2023; Anderson, 2013; Dinçer & Hacıoğlu, 2017).

Research Methods

A qualitative methodology is applied in this research, utilizing the case study approach. Case study at PT. LMC, especially in partnership operations. The main problem faced by PT. LMC's implementation of its partnership concept is directly related to the company's strategic analysis. The partnership concept, which includes capital assistance, purchasing seeds, fertilizer, and assistance from the seeding to harvest process, shows that PT. LMCs adopt partnership strategies as an integral part of their business approach. However, obstacles in implementing such programs may reflect the need to revise or optimize the

partnership strategy adopted. In the context of company strategy analysis, the competitive advantage of PT. LMC, primarily focusing on values such as family and honesty, is also a key element. The family nature applied to farmer partners creates positive differentiation in the market. However, challenges arise in ensuring that these values are not only a concept but also reflected in every aspect of implementing the partnership strategy.

Analysis of company strategy at PT. LMC can involve an in-depth evaluation of the success of implementing the partnership concept, including effectiveness in providing capital assistance, mentoring, and a personal approach to partner farmers. Revision or improvement of the partnership strategy may be needed to overcome the obstacles that arise while ensuring that kinship and honesty are not just slogans but are integrated into every strategic step of the company.

The formulation of this problem can only be answered through a naturalist paradigm approach, where understanding human behavior is interpreted by the frame of reference for behavior itself. This approach requires in-depth understanding and adaptation to social situations in the research context. Therefore, the research focus is limited to PT. LMC in partnership activities because operational problems that arise in partnerships cannot be considered to occur with certainty or are relevant to other companies. Thus, the solutions found for the issues in this research cannot be generally applied to other corporate contexts.

Research Subjects

This research involves informants at the director level. The two informants used in this study are the president and finance directors. The selection of these two informants is based on the consideration that directors play a crucial role in making strategic decisions for the company, and they are also responsible for formulating the company's vision and mission. The author can obtain a small number of informants for their research; the researcher can reduce the number of informants if they feel that the information received is sufficient, supported by corroborating documentation (Heryana, 2022). For instance, the research is designed to involve three or four informants. Still, only two informants must provide the required information alongside the supporting documentation.

Consequently, the researcher can cease the data collection once adequate information is obtained from these two informants, further bolstered by relevant document analysis (Khosiah et al., 2017). This approach allows the researcher to efficiently utilize resources and time while ensuring the acquired data remains relevant, qualitative, and supported by robust documentation (Sugiyono, 2010). The types and criteria of informants can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Informant Criteria

Position	Criteria
President director	The highest decision-maker in the company
	Have a deep understanding of the industry or market.
	Engage in strategic communication with stakeholders.
	Determine the strategic direction within the company.
	Formulate the company's vision, mission, and goals
Director of Finance	Formulate strategic policies in terms of company finances.
	Have good risk management in the financial sector.
	Have an understanding of the company's financial strategy.
	Analyze the company's financial performance.
	Get involved in formulating company strategy.

Types and Sources

The research relies on qualitative data, encompassing standard operating procedures, job descriptions, and field activity implementation. Quantitative data comprises financial reports, billing invoices, purchase orders, and inventory reports. Data collection involved both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through observations and interviews, while secondary data was sourced from financial report documents, inventory reports, and purchase order reports.

Data Collection Instruments and Procedures

The research instrument and data were collected using interviews, observation, and documentation.

1. **Interview.** The interview process carried out in this research was aimed at the directors and management of PT. LMC to find out the company's strategy analysis for partnership activities. A list of interview questions can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Interview Guidelines

Analysis Method	Question
Industry Analysis	What are the typical attributes of the sector in which the company operates?
	What are the main trends affecting the industry today?
	Who are the company's main competitors in the industry?
	Are there significant barriers to entry in this industry?
	What is the level of bargaining power of buyers and suppliers in the industry?
Market Analysis	What market segment is the company's primary target?
	What is the company's ideal customer profile?
	Are there market growth opportunities that still need to be explored?

Analysis Method	Question
	What is the company's brand perception among consumers?
	Are there market trends that could influence the company's strategy?
SWOT analysis	What are the company's unique strengths that give it a competitive advantage?
	What weaknesses might limit the company's growth or sustainability?
	What opportunities can the company exploit for growth?
	What external threats can hinder a company's success?
	How can companies maximize strengths and opportunities and overcome weaknesses and threats?
Risk Analysis	What are the main risks facing companies in this industry?
	How do companies identify and manage these risks?
	Are there external factors that could affect operational stability?
	How is the business continuity plan implemented in the face of risk?
	What is the company's risk tolerance level in decision-making?
Company Analysis	What is the company's business model, and how does the company generate revenue?
	How does the company's organizational structure support business strategy?
	Does the company have a competitive advantage in human resources or technology?
	How has the company's financial performance been in recent years?
	How do companies measure their sustainability and social impact?

2. **Observation.** The observational activities conducted in this research encompass a series of concrete actions to observe various aspects of the partnership directly. For example, in the farmer partner search phase, researchers will visit locations where farmers could become partners. They may interact directly with farmers, observe farming practices, and understand the needs and challenges farmers face in their practices.

Furthermore, researchers will be present during field partnership activities when farmers and other parties are engaged in agricultural activities such as seeding, crop maintenance, and harvesting. They will observe how farmers and company partners cooperate and how the farming process is conducted in daily practice.

Moreover, researchers will also observe the loan disbursement process regarding working capital and other facilities provided to partner farmers. They will monitor how the loan application process is carried out, the criteria for determining loan recipients, and its impact on farmers' agricultural activities. Observational activities also include directly monitoring the harvesting process, where researchers will follow farmers and harvesting

teams during the harvest. They will observe operational efficiency, the quality of harvested products, and any risk mitigation efforts undertaken during this process. By directly observing various stages of the partnership like these, researchers can gain in-depth insights into the dynamics, challenges, and opportunities involved in agricultural partnership practices. Observation activities carried out in this research aim better to understand the situation and conditions of partnership operational activities, starting from searching for farmer partners, partnership activities in the field, providing loans, harvest activities, and other activities.

3. **Documentation.** Documentation includes the collection of written, visual, or recorded materials relevant to the research topic. This document contains official documents, meeting minutes, posters and banners, company information leaflets, financial reports, and other documents. Through this document, an analysis of the company's strategy can be carried out.

Data analysis technique

The process of data analysis techniques carried out in this research is guided by Miles and Huberman's statement Sugiyono (2010), which consists of four stages, namely:

1. The data acquisition process involves field activities, which include interviews, surveys, observations, and documentation to collect the necessary information.
2. Data reduction is done by summarizing information, extracting the essence of the data, focusing on critical aspects, identifying themes and patterns, and eliminating irrelevant elements. Data are organized in such a way as to allow explanation and verification of conclusions.
3. Data presentation involves creating a written report detailing the results of interviews, observations, and questionnaires after the data has been collected and processed. These results are then compared with relevant theories.
4. At this stage, conclusions are drawn based on the results of data reduction, answering the research problems that have been identified.

The series of data analysis can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Data Analysis

Data Validity/Validity Criteria

Data validity or data validity criteria must meet the following requirements:

1. Internal validity. Internal validity can be obtained if the researcher concludes the problem or event that occurred. The process carried out for internal validity uses triangulation. This research uses source triangulation, namely collecting and searching for the truth of certain information through various sources. This research conducted interviews by asking questions to certain parties with essential roles and who is responsible for determining PT operational policies. LMC is at the director level, compared with company documents obtained, such as financial reports and directors' meeting minutes. This interview was done to get accurate interview results in implementing company strategy analysis at PT. LMC so that valid data and information can be obtained from various sources.

Figure 3. Triangulation of Three Data Sources

2. External validity

External validity results from the sustainability of research findings that can be generalized beyond the case study used in this research to form a unique interpretation of an event or incident. This research uses market analysis, industry analysis, company analysis, SWOT analysis, and risk analysis. There have been many studies using these theories, and if PT. LMC applies as in previous studies, followed by PT. LMC has successfully implemented a strategic analysis process in the company's partnership activities.

3. Reliability

Reliability aims to obtain confidence that this research can be replicated or repeated by following data collection procedures, applying triangulation, and using data analysis to minimize errors and bias in research (Yin, 1994). The results of this research can be used as material for further research on the same topic, namely reviewing comprehensive corporate strategy analysis in each company.

Discussion

Company background

PT. LMC is a company operating in the agribusiness sector since 2012. PT. LMC has several operational activities, such as plantation processing, production, and partnerships with local farmers. PT. LMC acts as a supplier of raw materials for making Essential Oil (EO), the processing of which is carried out by a company still under the same parent company as PT. LMC in the Lampung region. To achieve the targets set by the management of PT. LMC does not only on its plantation products but also on PT. LMC also develops partnerships with farmers to obtain the desired raw materials.

Figure 4. PT LMC's position in the Holding Group

This partnership program with farmers is PT's management strategy. LMC uses an association that has the following vision and mission:

Table 3. Vision and Mission of PT. LMC

Vision	Enabling local farmers and producers to achieve maximum productivity
Mission	Developing plant cultivation
	Opening new job opportunities for residents
	Increase local original income community income and reduce income inequality.
	We are providing benefits for the company regarding income and cost efficiency.

Figure 5. PT Partnership Vision. LMC

Moreover, the values espoused by PT. LMC's "Partnership Synergized" means a partnership full of synergy and collaboration will produce maximum performance.

Figure 6. PT Partnership Value. LMC

In general, the partnership concept offered by PT. LMC is providing capital assistance in purchasing seeds and fertilizer and monitoring staff so that farmer partners can produce plants with the quality and quantity expected by the company. Capital assistance is a loan from the company to the farmer, and payments are made from the farmer's harvest. Details of the rights and obligations of farmer partners and PT. LMC can be seen in Table 4 below

Table 4. Rights and Obligations of Farmer Partners and PT. LMC

Farmer Partners		PT. LMC	
Right	Obligation	Right	Obligation
Get supervision from PT staff. LMC	Providing land	Get full participation from farmer partners	Purchase farmer partners' harvests
Get seed and fertilizer loan assistance	Providing labor	Get installment payments from farmer partner loans	Providing capital assistance for purchasing seeds and fertilizer
Get enough knowledge	Carry out maintenance (fertilizing, watering) according to PT directions. LMC	Provide direction to Farmer Partners	Provide supervision for farmer partners
Get a guarantee of harvest results purchased by PT. LMC	Make loan installment payments after the harvest by compensating the harvest minus the loan installments to PT.LMC	-	Provide sufficient knowledge for farmer partners.

So, PT staff. LMC will assist farmer partners in the seeding process and care to harvest. PT. LMC employees will share their knowledge with farmers so they can conduct the maintenance process independently. The harvest results will likely be based on the targets determined by PT. LMC. This farmer partnership program has only been implemented in the East Java, West Java, and Central Java areas.

Competitive advantage is determining a company's strategy based on the superiority of goods or services compared to other options (Cegliński, 2017). By knowing competitive advantage, a company will have more opportunities to get consumers' attention—a competitive advantage for the partnership program carried out by PT. LMC focuses more on *value* but also pays attention to the costs incurred in the partnership program—the value concept offered by PT. LMC is unique compared to competitors; if competitors aim more, they get maximum results, and there is also a lack of attention to farmer partners, PT. LMC provides a partnership concept that is full of family characteristics. PT. LMC is one of the companies from a large group in Indonesia that has unique values and culture, so this is what is offered to farmer partners. The central values brought are kinship and honesty, so these advantages are applied to farmer partners by approaching their side by considering farmers not as partners but as part of a family. The degree of family with a partner is undoubtedly higher than that of a family because no family expects its family members to fail. Therefore, as a family, we will provide the best

performance and processes and be honest. Honesty is essential in all matters, whether as a family or partner. Without honesty, a synergistic relationship will not be achieved. From these two central values, PT. LMC has formed a partnership concept of synergy and collaboration to produce maximum performance.

Analysis Performed

To create strategic partnership planning, PT. LMC carries out several analyses such as market analysis, industry analysis, company analysis, SWOT analysis, and risk analysis with the following details:

Market Analysis

It is an analysis or implementation activity to study various problems regarding market conditions targeted by the organization (Xing, 2023), such as the PT partnership program. LMC is the EO market, including citronella, eucalyptus, essentials, cloves, and other EO products. The development of EO is increasing all the time, especially after the world experienced the Covid 19 pandemic, which made people more aware and pay attention to health. EO products are health products, so it is a perfect opportunity for companies to market EO products. The largest EO destination countries for India's export markets are Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia, America, and India, as can be seen in the following graph, which has increased from year to year. Therefore, from a market perspective, the need for EO products still has a substantial product sales potential.

Figure 7. Growth in Indonesian Essential Oil Exports

Source: <https://www.trademap.org/>

Industrial Analysis

The following analysis is a market evaluation tool businesses and companies use to understand and analyze the level of competition in a particular industry (Vásquez-Lavín et al., 2020). Hence, conducting multiple assessments concerning industry competitiveness, the potential for new entrants, the availability of substitute products, and the bargaining power of customers and suppliers is imperative.

Table 5. Industrial Analysis of PT. LMC

Strength Analysis	Explanation of Analysis
Competitive rivalry	Only a few large companies are still involved in the EO field, but most have been in the EO field for a long time, so they have quality product names and are well-known in the eyes of significant customers. This factor can affect the value of a product and the EO's price and production costs.
The threat of new entrants	Relatively high, this is generally caused by employees of a company engaged in the EO sector leaving and setting up their own business in the same field (EO). That factor can affect the price of commodity goods and the amount of supply the company expects.
The threat of substitute products	That factor does not affect commodity prices because EO oil types cannot be replaced and have their characteristics and functions.
Bargaining power of buyers	High, especially for EO commodities in excess supply (for example, citronella oil). This factor can affect commodity prices and the product quality that consumers expect.
Bargaining power of suppliers	It is low because EO variations are slight. However, suppliers have high power for products not produced in large quantities and sought after by consumers (for example, patchouli and lamp oil). This factor can increase the purchasing price of products made by farmer partners and the expected product quality.

The table above shows that the potential for competition is still wide open because only a few companies operate in the essential Oil sector and have the same type of business as this company. As accompanying material for industry analysis, attached is data on the development of plantation products for several plants commonly used in the partnership process, such as citronella, patchouli, and other EO products, as shown in Figure 8.

Tabel Dinamis

 Unduh Data

Jenis Tanaman Perkebunan Rakyat	Luas Areal Tanaman Perkebunan Rakyat Menurut Jenis Tanaman (Ribu Hektar)						
	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015
Panili	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cengkeh	566.60	567.50	566.60	560.30	551.80	535.90	526.60
Tembakau	200.00	229.70	234.30	204.40	201.80	155.60	208.30
Sereh wangi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nilam	17.40	12.20	11.60	21.40	20.50	19.60	18.60

Figure 8. Growth of Indonesian Plantation Products
 Source: <https://www.bps.go.id>

Company Analysis

The company's fundamental analysis stages aim to identify the most prospective and profitable industries (KULAK & KAHRAMAN, 2005). The most profitable prospects for an industry or company can be seen in its financial reports. Because PT. LMC is a closed company (family company), so its data cannot be shared openly. The following are the results of the analysis of existing financial reports :

Table 6. Financial Ratio Analysis of PT. LMC

Financial ratios	Remark	Results
Return on Assets	$(\text{Net Profit} / \text{Average Assets}) \times 100\%$	4.08%
Return on Equity	$\text{Earnings After Tax (EAT)} / \text{Total Equity} \times 100\%$	5.86%
Profit margin	$\text{Net Profit After Tax (EAT)} / \text{Net Sales} \times 100\%$	5.10%
Gross profit margin	$(\text{Revenue} - \text{COGS}) / \text{Revenue}$	11.92%
Current ratio	$\text{Current Assets} / \text{Current Liabilities} \times 100\%$	94.77%
Liability to Equity Ratio	$\text{Total debt} / \text{Equity}$	26.15%
Liabilities to Assets Ratio	$[(\text{Short Term Liabilities} + \text{Long Term Liabilities}) \div \text{Total Assets}] \times 100$	18.22%
Cash Ratio	$(\text{Cash} + \text{Securities}) / \text{Current Liabilities} \times 100\%$	76.23%
Quick ratio	$(\text{Current assets} - \text{Inventory}) / \text{Current Liabilities} \times 100\%$	90.15%

From the analysis of the financial statements, the company's financial condition is still quite good; In Table 7 there is the analysis carried out on the financial ratios.

Table 7. Analysis of the financial statements

Financial ratios	Results	Analyze
Return on Assets	4.08%	The asset's ability to generate profits is still quite good
Return on Equity	5.86%	The company's ability to use its capital is still quite good
Profit margin	5.10%	Not to the maximum, but still showing quite good growth
Gross profit margin	11.92%	Still in line with the expected target
Current ratio	94.77%	The condition of assets is still higher than debt, so the condition is still good
Liability to Equity Ratio	26.15%	Relatively high at this ratio but still in pretty good condition
Liabilities to Assets Ratio	18.22%	The lower this ratio, the better the company's condition
Cash Ratio	76.23%	The company's cash condition is still good
Quick ratio	90.15%	The company's conditions for paying off its total liabilities, both short and long-term, can be done using a faster method

Analysis of financial reports shows that the company's financial condition is still quite good.

SWOT analysis

In this analysis, PT. LMC has mapped this partnership process's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The results of this analysis are the result of discussions with the field operations team and management, with the following results:

Table 8. SWOT Analysis of PT. LMC

PT. LMC	
Strength (Strength)	Weakness
The company has sufficient funds.	Number of Human Resources (HR) covering the partnership area
Have sufficient knowledge	Insufficient human resource capabilities
It has unique values and culture.	One of Indonesia's most prominent groups, the Lampung factory, must prepare to process the partnership
results.	Expenditures depend on the condition of the partner farmer's land.
Opportunity	Threat
The essential oils (EO) market is growing.	Several competitors, such as PT. Indesso and CV. XOSO has been involved in the EO field for a long time.

The lifestyle of people who want to use herbal/natural products	Rapid EO oil price fluctuations
There are still many EOs that have not been developed in Indonesia	An uncertain climate can affect the output of partner farmers
EO ingredients that are easy to find in Indonesia	Partnership program offers are more attractive than competitors
	Farmer partners must fulfill their commitments.
	Bad debts occur in receivables/loans from farmer partners.

Table 9. SWOT Analysis of Farmer Partners

Farmer Partners	
Strength (Strength)	Weaknesses
Has garden land	Land conditions that do not comply with PT standards. LMC
Have a workforce that is ready to work	Access to the garden location is not easy
Farmers' enthusiasm for better results	The land area does not meet PT standards. LMC
Opportunities	Threats
Job opportunities open	Partner (PT. LMC) did not carry out its commitment
Have a partner in gardening	An uncertain climate can affect farmers' output
Gain knowledge in plant cultivation	Yield specifications do not meet standards
Obtain a guarantee that the garden produce will be sold to PT. LMC	
Get a loan first from PT. LMC for plantation operations	

From the results of the SWOT analysis, it can be seen that the company still has considerable strength in finance, human resources and a good culture. These strengths position the company to survive and maintain competitiveness in facing existing market competition. However, existing weaknesses must be immediately corrected or developed, such as improving the capabilities of good human resources, so that it is hoped that productive partnership results will be obtained with good resources.

Risk Analysis

Risk is an event that can affect the goals of an organization. Risk can be a threat or an opportunity when facing a problem. This risk analysis can be mapped into strategic, operational, financial, and hazard risks, and the identification process can use the results of discussions, SWOT analysis, and other methods. The following are details of risk identification in the partnership program:

Table 10. Risk Identification

Types of Risk	Risk Details
Strategic Risk	Competitors have more advanced technology.
	The better partnership offers than competitors.
	More advanced competitor R&D capabilities
	EO oil price fluctuations
Operational risk	Incompetent HR
	Insufficient number of human resources
	Factory capacity in Lampung needs to be increased.
	Lampung production machines still need to be ready.
	Farmer partners do not carry out instructions from PT. LMC staff.
	Farmer partners must fulfill their commitments.
Financial risk	Excessive spending
	Farmer partner receivables are uncollectible (bad debt)
	Explosive/high operational costs for employees
Risk of Danger	Employee Death
	Employee Health
	Unfavorable climate

Determination of Strategic Plans and Strategy Implementation

After carrying out several analyses, the management of PT. LMC will determine several strategic steps to complete the expected goals. Apart from providing opportunities and increasing income for farmer partners, this partnership aims to increase income and cost efficiency for the company. One way to increase revenue is to get the quantity of raw materials according to the Lampung factory's production target/needs and have the expected quality.

Meanwhile, the cost efficiency of this partnership program is that companies can invest small amounts. Investment in plantations is costly, including land purchase, legal fees, infrastructure development, asset investment, and others. Just for information, PT. LMC has a plantation in the East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) area with a total investment cost of 22 billion Rupiah with a total land area of 30 Ha and does not include monthly fixed costs such as salary costs, food costs, maintenance costs, fuel costs and others with total costs an average of IDR 300,000,000 per month and new plants can produce productive results in the 8th year and beyond. So, the company calculates to get the Break Even Point (BEP) around the 20th year. Table 11 below shows the stages or phases of clove plant development focused on NTT plantations.

Table 11. Clove Plant Development Phases

Phase / Phase	Duration
Nursery	Years 1-3
Planting	4th year
Maintenance	Years 5-8
Harvest	9th year
Harvest Process per Period	Every year after the 9th year

So it can be concluded that investment for plantations is vast and takes a long time, so management prefers the partnership concept of LMCn, which has the following advantages:

1. The company does not need to invest in land because the land uses the land of farmer partners
2. There is no need to pay salary costs because the workforce uses Farmer Partner staff.
3. There is no need to pay other monthly costs.
4. All fertilization and seed purchase costs will be borne by the Farmer Partners even in the initial stages of PT. LMC will provide loan assistance. The loan will be deducted when Mitra Farmer sells its harvest to PT. LMC.

Even though it has several advantages, this partnership model still has several strategic risks, which is a significant concern for PT management. LMC. Table 12 is an explanation of strategic steps to deal with these problems:

Table 12. Strategic Plan

Strategic Plan Category	Information
Increase company value	Improving human resource competency by recruiting agricultural staff who have experience and competence
	Provide training on how to communicate and negotiate with employees.
	Pay attention to the R&D process to discover new varieties.
Retaining Customers	Providing quality raw materials according to specified standards
	We are providing quantities according to Lampung factory requirements.
	Providing an offer for the EO type that the Lampung factory will produce
Investment	Invest in research and development
Eliminate/replace activities or partnership relationships.	Look for new areas of partnership to find various types of farmer partners and open up business opportunities for them.
	Looking for farmer partners who are competent and have good abilities
	Providing attractive facilities/programs for competent farmer partners
Risk management	Monitor existing risks

Implementation of the strategy carried out by PT. LMC is good enough and has been paying attention to several aspects, such as risk management and improving the quality of partnership staff by providing regular training. By giving good training facilities, officers' knowledge will also increase, and suitable direction will be given to partner farmers so that they produce good quality products according to company standards. The strategic partnership model with farmers that is carried out is more towards the Delta model, where this model provides benefits for both parties. Creating good partnership conditions for farmers involves efforts to establish equitable agreements and foster collaborative relationships; several things must be done well by the company and partner farmers, as shown in Figure 9, namely:

1. Mutual Goals (Joint goals)

Farmer partners and companies have the same goals: to obtain better income, grow crops, and benefit all existing stakeholders (directors, management, employees, farmer partners, suppliers, farming communities, government, and so on).

2. Continuous Improvement and Innovation The company will continue to improve and provide the best knowledge to the company and farmer partners so that the plants cultivated will give maximum results and quality that meets expectations. The improvement process is that the company assists partner farmers with experts who are competent in experience and education.

3. Effective Dispute Resolution

It is hoped that there will be no disputes in establishing partnership cooperation because if a conflict or dispute results in the goal not being achieved, both parties do not expect it. However, to avoid the risk of disputes in the future, the company uses a cooperation agreement system with farmer partners.

After these three steps have been carried out, company partnership activities should be able to run synergistically and produce optimal results (following company values that synergize collaboration). From the explanation of the company's strategy, it can be concluded that it is still in line with the company's vision and mission, which aims to improve the welfare of partner farmers by opening business opportunities, cultivating plants, and generating income and cost efficiency.

Figure 9. Delta Model Partnership Strategy

Good planning will only be good if it is implemented or carried out. In the process of executing existing plans, there are unrealized strategies, implemented strategies in the field (deliberate strategies), strategies that emerge without planning (emergent strategies), and successful strategy implementation (realized strategies), as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 10. Intended, Intentional, Realized, Emergent, and Unrealized Strategies
 Source: Mintzberg et al. (2005)

The company delegates its implementation to middle to lower-line management in this partnership program strategy. To reduce the possibility of failure in implementing the plan, management takes a perfect collaborative approach, takes a persuasive approach, carries out regular monitoring, and forms more straightforward lines of coordination and responsibility to facilitate the decision-making process so that the most important thing is that every employee understands their duties and responsibilities—his responsibility.

Table 13. Implementation of Farmer Partnership Strategy

Implementation Stage	Activities performed
Early stage	Looking for potential farmer partners
	Take a persuasive approach to farmer partners/farmer groups.
	Approach local officials such as village heads and others
	Explain the benefits of cultivating plants and their economic benefits.
	Providing partnership program offers to prospective farmer partners.
	Communicate effectively and regularly with potential farmer partners and farming communities.
Demoplot stage	Carry out a demonstration process for plant plots on partner farmer's land.
	Monitor regularly

Implementation Stage	Activities performed
	Providing support in terms of fertilizer, seed fertilizer (company costs)
	Provide counseling and knowledge to farmer partners regularly.
	Carrying out regular communication and evaluation processes
	We provide loan assistance through fertilizer, manure, and seeds.
	Monitor the progress of the demo plot process to ensure that it meets the specified quality and results.
	Showing pilot results to prospective farmer partners and farming communities will attract them to partner farmers.
Partnership Stage	Make partnership cooperation agreements with farmer partners.
	Make a thorough demographic and topographic analysis.
	Providing infrastructure to support partnership programs
	Monitor regularly
	Provide counseling and knowledge to farmer partners regularly.
	We provide loan assistance through fertilizer, manure, and seeds.
	We are providing support in terms of fertilizer and seeds.
	Providing knowledge to partner farmers
	Provide support during the harvest season.
	We provide loan assistance through fertilizer, manure, and seeds.
	Regularly monitor farmer loan amounts to stay within budget.
	Conduct regular evaluations and communications.
	Looking for potential farmer partners

Apart from implementing the farmer partnership strategy, the management of PT. LMC also carries out a process of minimizing operational and financial risks, which can be seen in Table 14 below:

Table 14. Operational and Financial Risk Treatment

Types of Risk	Risk Details	Risk Treatment
Operational risk	Incompetent HR	Looking for quality human resources both in terms of experience and competence
	Insufficient number of human resources	Conduct regular evaluations between farmer partner regions and the amount of human resources they have
	Factory capacity in Lampung needs to be improved.	Coordinate with the Lampung Factory if there will be purchases of raw materials.
	The production machines in Lampung are not yet ready	Coordinate with the Lampung Factory if there will be purchases of raw materials
	Partner farmers need to carry out instructions from PT officers. sustainable	Conduct regular approaches and supervision and provide attractive incentive programs for farmer partners.
	Farmer partners need to fulfill their commitments.	Make a cooperation agreement and explain the rights, obligations, and consequences if Mitra Tani needs an exemplary commitment.
	Excessive spending	Carry out cost control and report actual vs budget periodically.
Financial risk	Farmer partner receivables are uncollectible (bad debt)	Carry out the billing process effectively and coordinate with the operational team
	Explosive/high operational costs for employees	Carry out cost control and report actual vs budget periodically.

The process of determining and implementing the partnership strategy has been carried out to date, and the evaluation and monitoring process continues to be carried out periodically. It is hoped that the results of this strategy will remain measurable and meet expectations. This partnership program has been running in the Java region (East et al.). His party is in the process of opening farmer partnerships in the Lampung and East Nusa Tenggara regions. So, the determined and implemented strategy continues to follow the company's Vision, Mission, and Values. This partnership program's results still need improvement, but it provides pretty good growth. Buying the harvest to resell it only provides a profit of around +/- 6%. However, with the high continuity and development of the EO market, the potential for continuation of this partnership program is enormous. To stay safe in this industry, companies must conduct regular market analysis, develop information technology well, and be aware of external potential and threats. In the future, implementing the company's strategy will allow the company to continue to use the current strategy by carrying out several innovations adapted to technological and

information developments. For a long-term strategy, the company must pay attention to all conditions that will occur, as previously explained.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusion

PT. LMC, which runs a partnership program with farmers, has developed a strategy and implementation process. This strategy can be implemented well in the Java Island region (East et al.). It will even create a partnership program with Lampung and Nusa Tenggara farmers. East. Companies can increase partnerships with local farmers by maintaining a competitive advantage by providing good value and having their characteristics.

Partnership program carried out by PT. LMC remains aligned with the vision, mission, and values implemented. The company's vision aims to enable local farmers and producers to achieve maximum productivity and increase income, improving the standard of living of partner farmers. To achieve the vision and mission and implement company values, the management of PT. LMC makes strategic plans using the Delta Model approach and considers the company's strengths and weaknesses, from opportunities to external threats. Several analyses have been carried out to measure the potential of this partnership program, such as market analysis, industry analysis, company analysis, SWOT analysis, and risk analysis to benefit the company in determining and implementing company strategy. This partnership program benefits both parties and PT. The LMC partnership program still provides good benefits for various parties/stakeholders so that it can be continued and developed.

Suggestion

Practical advice for PT. LMC is open to current conditions. Indeed PT. LMC has unique characteristics in terms of family values and honesty, but there is no eternal strategy because PT. LMC must be sensitive and more alert to strategic activities carried out by competitors and developments in the EO market, potential markets, and types of EO that will provide potential markets. Suppose all these possible threats can be identified. In that case, the company will be more focused on implementing strategic programs; for example, the research and development team discovered EO products from plant "X," so the partnership team immediately carried out land surveys and potential farmer partners to cultivate plant "X." " So in this way, the company is not left behind by its competitors.

Apart from that, companies are advised to continue developing information and technology to provide information to farmer partners. Farmers' productivity levels will continue to create and deliver optimum results with the knowledge that continues to grow and be tested.

Meanwhile, future research can further discuss other factors in determining company policies, such as implementing effective governance and implementing information

systems holistically so that they can provide more practical information and competencies. Apart from that, this analysis can be applied to other industries.

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